

Prosumers Contribution in Youtube- A Paradigm Shift from Consume to Create – A Study

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Dr.P.Natesan

Dean and Head, Department of Commerce, P.K.R. Arts College for Women Gobichettipalayam

Abstract

YouTube, a video sharing website, whose revenues in 2007 were noted as “not material” in a regulatory filing. In June 2008, a Forbes magazine article projected the 2008 revenue at \$200 million, noting progress in advertising sales. In January 2012, it was estimated that visitors to YouTube spent an average of 15 minutes a day on the site, in contrast to the four or five hours a day spent by a typical US citizen watching television. In 2012, YouTube’s revenue from its ads program was estimated at \$3.7 billion. In 2013 it nearly doubled and estimated to hit \$5.6 billion according to e-Marketer, others estimated 4.7 billion, The vast majority of videos on YouTube are free to view and supported by advertising. In May 2013, YouTube introduced a trial scheme of 53 subscription channels with prices ranging from \$0.99 to \$6.99 a month. The move was seen as an attempt to compete with other providers of online subscription services such as Netflix and Hulu. In 2017, viewers on average watch YouTube on mobile devices for more than an hour every day.

Keywords: YouTube, Videos, Upload, Google.

Origin of Youtube

Chad Hurley, Steve Chen and Jawed Karim founded YouTube on 14th February 2005. YouTube is an American Video sharing website. It is an Internet Video Hosting Service Industry. Its head quarters are at San Bruno, California. Alphabet Inc, is the owner and Susan Wojcicki is the CEO. The founders were former PayPal employees. The base for origin of YouTube arises when, Hurley and Chen built up the thought for YouTube amid the early long periods of 2005, after they had encountered trouble sharing recordings that hosted been shot at a supper get-together at Chen’s condo in San Francisco. Karim did not go to the gathering and denied that it had happened, yet Chen remarked that that YouTube was established after a supper party “was presumably fortified by advertising thoughts around making a story that was truly absorbable”. Thus YouTube emerged and came into the world market and started serving Worldwide, except some of the blocked countries.

YouTube allows users to upload, view, rate, share, add to favorites, report, comment on videos, and subscribe to other users. It offers a wide variety of user-generated and corporate media videos. Available contents includes Video clips, TV show clips, music video, short and

documentary films, audio recordings, movie trailers, live streams, and other content such as video blogging, short original videos, and educational videos. Most of the content on YouTube is uploaded by individuals, but media corporations including CBS, the BBC, Vevo, and Hulu offer some of their material via YouTube as part of the YouTube partnership program. Unregistered users can only watch videos on the site, while registered users are permitted to upload an unlimited number of videos and add comments to videos. Videos deemed potentially inappropriate are available only to registered users affirming themselves to be at least 18 years old.

The inspiration for YouTube first came from Janet Jackson's role in the 2004 Super Bowl incident and later from the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami said Karim. He could not easily find video clips of either event online. It made his to come with the idea of a video sharing site. Hurley and Chen pointed out that the original idea for YouTube was a video version of an online dating service, and had been influenced by the website Hot or Not.

The domain name www.youtube.com was activated on February 14, 2005, and the website was developed over the subsequent months. "Me At the Zoo" was the first video in YouTube which shows co-founder Jawed Karim at the San Diego Zoo, which is uploaded on April 23, 2005. YouTube offered the public a beta test of the site in May 2005. The first video to reach one million views was a Nike advertisement featuring Ronaldinho in November 2005. Following a \$3.5 million investment from Sequoia Capital in November, the site launched officially on December 15, 2005, by which time the site was receiving 8 million views a day.

On 13th November 2006, Google bought this service site for US\$1.65 billion. Now YouTube is one of Google's subsidiaries. Sociologist Philip N. Howard quoted an activist's succinct description that organizing the political unrest involved using "Facebook to schedule the protests, Twitter to coordinate, and YouTube to tell the world."

Benefits of Watching Youtube

- It helps the students of gain knowledge from professors across global.
- Access of resources at anytime and anywhere is possible without any payment.
- Skill of the uploader can be made use of.
- Enables the students to study with the high professional teacher.
- The videos uploaded gives hope to the viewers.
- Students need not go to classroom; they can gain knowledge by sitting at the home.
- Video's on how to make up, videos on how to cook, videos on how to make different hairstyles etc., act as a source of real life happenings.
- It is both audio-visual medium and acts as a big digital library.
- All kind of entertainment like movie, music, serials, game show etc., which can release out stress.
- There is more security for age group for viewing video.

Disadvantage of Youtube

YouTube is one of the two-edged swords which one side is good and another side is bad.

- There is no distinction made between good and the bad one. Videos on robbery, theft, terrorism, suicide etc., will promote skill of violence.
- Uncensored videos on sexual harassment clips may deviate the viewers.
- There are chances of pirated videos and songs that might affect the copy right issue.
- Because of the freedom of uploading video there are many video was uploaded by another people and it effect to the whole life of the owner.
- There are many contents foster to use violence to the young generation or to the country.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are

- To find the awareness level of the respondents in uploading the videos in YouTube.
- To know the preference of the social media for video upload.
- To find out the earnings made for the video's uploaded by the respondents.

Statement of the Problem

Google AdSense is a program which targets ads according to audience content of the site. YouTube earns revenue from Google AdSense for advertising. The site grew rapidly and, in July 2006, the company announced that more than 65,000 new videos were being uploaded every day, and that the site was receiving 100 million video views per day. According to data published by market research company comScore, YouTube is the dominant provider of online video in the United States, with a market share of around 43% and more than 14 billion views of videos in May 2010.

Scope of the Study

In May 2011, 48 hours of new recordings were transferred to the site each moment, which expanded to 60 hours consistently in January 2012, 100 hours consistently in May 2013, 300 hours consistently in November 2014, and 400 hours consistently in February 2017. The site has 800 million one of kind clients a month. It is evaluated that in 2007 YouTube expended as much transmission capacity as the whole Internet in 2000. As indicated by outsider web examination suppliers, Alexa and SimilarWeb, YouTube is the second-most visited site on the planet, as of December 2016; SimilarWeb additionally records YouTube as the best TV and video site internationally, pulling in excess of 15 billion guests for every month. This made the researcher to know the awareness of the various steps involved in video uploading, its impact and the earnings made by the respondents.

Source: www.youtube.org/statistics

Research Design and Sample Size

The researcher has adopted a Non-probability Sampling Technique in order to select the sample from a relatively large population framework in each organization. Samples were selected by using convenient sampling procedure. A well structured questionnaire was framed and the respondents were asked to fill. The researcher has selected 40 as the sample size for the study.

Findings of the Study

The findings of the study are:

1) Specify your Occupational status _____

Table 1 Occupation of the Respondents

S.No	Occupation	No.of Respondents	%
1	Government Employee	4	10
2	Private Employee	15	38
3	Businessman	3	8
4	Professionals (IT., etc.,)	18	44
	Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference

It is evident from the Table 1 that, 44% of the respondents are Professional people, 38 of them are Private employees, 10% are Government Employees and 8% of them are Businessman.

2) Mention the social media you choose for uploading?

Figure 1

3) How long you have been uploading videos?

Table 2 Duration of Uploading Video's

S.No	Duration	No.of Respondents	%
1	Less than 1 year(Beginner)	11	27
2	Between 1 – 2 yrs	12	30
3	Between 2 - 3 yrs	10	25
4	Between 3 – 4 yrs	6	15
5	Above 4 yrs	1	3
	Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference

It is known from the Table 2 that, 30% of the respondents are uploading the videos between 1-2 years, 27% of them are uploading less than one year, 25% of them between 2-3 years, 15 years of them between 3-4 years and 3% of them are uploading above 4 years.

4) What would you upload in YouTube?

Figure 2

5) How many upload you have made?

Table 3 Number of Upload's Made

S.No	No. of Upload's	No.of	%
1	Respondents	%	27
2	Between 0-5	2	5
3	Between 6- 10	7	18
4	Between 11 – 15	12	30
5	Between 16 – 20	10	25
	Above 20	9	22
	Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference

It is vivid from the above Table 3 that, 30% of the respondents have made between 11-15 uploads, 25% of them have uploaded between 16-20 and 5% of them have uploaded less than 5.

6) Where will you post your videos?

Figure 3

7) How much you earn per month through YouTube?

Table 4 Earnings Per Month

S.No	Earnings	No.of	%
1	Respondents	%	27
2	Less than Rs.10,000	8	20
3	Between Rs.10,001- Rs.20,000	12	30
4	Between Rs.20,001- Rs.30,000	10	25
5	Between Rs. 30,001- Rs.40,000	7	18
	Above Rs. 40,001	3	7
	Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference

The above Table 4 reveals that, 30% of the respondents earn between Rs. 10,001 – Rs. 20,000, 25% of them earn between 20,001-Rs.30,000, 20% of them earns less than 10,000, 18% of them earns between Rs.30,001-Rs.40,000 and 7% of them earns above Rs.40,001.

Result of Hypothesis Framed

Chi square test has been adopted to find out the result for the hypothesis formulated.

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between the choice of social media and their earnings per month.

For 3 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance, the table value is 7.81

Since the calculated value (1.1816) is less than the table value (7.81), at 5% level with 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is a relationship between number of uploads made and profile of web videos
For 3 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance, the table value is 7.81

The calculated value (5.04828) is less than the Table value (7.05). Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

Online video, particularly predominant player YouTube, has empowered independent ventures to achieve clients in manners beforehand open just to expansive organizations that could manage the cost of TV advertisements, and enables them to frame “mark channels”, track watcher measurements, and give instructional recordings to diminish the requirement for exorbitant client bolster. Vast organizations “amortize” the huge expense of their Super Bowl TV plugs by attempting to expand post-diversion video plays.

YouTube has concentrated on creating stations as opposed to making content as such, the stations dividing the group of onlookers into specialties similarly that decades sooner many specialty gathering of people digital TV stations divided the crowd recently commanded by the Big Three telecom companies. YouTube creates social effect and make mindfulness among people in general and society.